

The Dhoofar Mountains

Introduction

Under the United Nations' Agenda 2030, one indicator of progress towards the conservation of mountain ecosystems (SDG 15.4) is the percentage [%] coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity (**key biodiversity areas, KBAs**) by **protected areas (PAs)** (SDG 15.4.1). KBAs are areas that significantly contribute to the persistence of global biodiversity. Currently, the indicator is hosted by the UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (WCMC).

WCMC site-based: The indicator is officially calculated as the **average of the PA coverage of KBAs within a country that are considered mountainous** based on the WCMC mountain definition from 2000¹.

GMBA area-based: As an alternative, the Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (GMBA) calculates the indicator as the **ratio between the total area of protected KBAs and the total area of KBAs in mountains**, applying its latest mountain definition from 2022².

Unless mentioned otherwise, the data presented in this one-pager correspond to the GMBA area-based calculation approach, for mountain systems that have KBA (n = 267).

WCMC site-based versus GMBA area-based (temporal comparison)

The Dhoofar Mountains in an international context (2020)

In the left side figure, each point represents one mountain system and its indicator value with both the WCMC site-based and the GMBA area-based calculation approach. The Dhoofar Mountains are marked with the asterisk. Mountain systems close to the diagonal line have a similar indicator value for both calculation approaches, not taking into account the mountain area of a mountain system.

The Dhoofar Mountains, with a GMBA area-based **indicator value of 65.3 for 2020**, have a value lower than 93 other mountain systems. 173 mountain systems have a value lower than the Dhoofar Mountains.

Looking at the spatial disaggregation of the Dhoofar Mountains (overleaf), they span two countries and need a cross-border management.

¹ Kapos et al. (2000) doi:10.1079/9780851994468.0004

² Snethlage et al. (2022) doi:10.1038/s41597-022-01256-y

Mountain range level disaggregation of the GMBA area-based indicator for the Dhofar Mountains (2020)
Percentage of KBA cover versus percentage of KBA covered by PA

Sub-mountainsystem indicator values

From the one mountain range in the Dhofar Mountains, none are without KBA (pinkish coloring in the country map). The other range has an indicator value of 65.3% (left side figure). There are no fully protected mountain ranges important for biodiversity in the Dhofar Mountains.

Explore GMBA's global coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity by protected areas, visit:
gmba.unibe.ch/services/indicators/sdg_1541